

Review Article

Problems and prospects of silver universities

Aleksandr Levintov

Independent Researcher, Russia

Corresponding author

Aleksandr Levintov. PhD (Geography), Independent Researcher. Russia

Received: 18 Dec 2024

Accepted : 24 Nov 2024

Published: 28 Dec 2024

Copyright

©2024 Aleksandr Levintov

OPEN ACCESS

Introduction

Silver University is one of the cardinal and most promising projects of Moscow City University. At present, a network of such universities is being formed in the country and neighboring countries, independently building their development trajectories, very different in composition, content, and methodology of ageing pedagogy. This mosaic is an indicator of the viability of this innovation: reforms are always bureaucratically driven from above, transformations are driven from below, from real life.

This article examines three horizons of perspective:

- immediate
- foreseeable
- distant

They differ not only in their location on the time axis, but also, above all, ontologically. In this sense, the distant perspective can be tomorrow if it is sufficiently contrasted with the present.

On the other hand, within the selected topic, ontological contrast is reflected in the democratic situation and demographic processes, and, consequently, in the peculiarities of the education of silver age people, in the problems of silver universities and projects to resolve these problems. It should be emphasized that the stages and sequence of design and redesign depends not only on the remoteness of certain problems, but also on their complexity and the scale of the projects themselves.

Thus, the content of this article fits into the following matrix.

	horizons of perspective		
	near-term	foreseeable	distant
ontological period characterization			
demographic trend			
peculiarities of education for people of silver age			

critical issues of silver universities			
project proposals and pre-project ideas			

Near-term perspective

Ontological characterization of the period

Economic stagnation, growing isolation and lagging behind the leading countries, increasing ties with developing countries and final transition to the pool of developing countries and the status of a developing country (an obvious and familiar euphemism characterizing the lack of development), a tragic gap between the real situation of the country and the self-definition of the bulk of the population as residents of a highly developed superpower, a decisive refusal of honest confessions and assessments.

Demographic trend

In the foreseeable future, a noticeable drop in the birth rate and a decline in the adult male population in the age group of 20-30 years is expected, as well as an increase in the disproportion between married men and married women (approximately 70:100) in the same age group. This will undoubtedly lead, all other things being equal, to a relative increase in the share of pensioners and, as a consequence, to the attraction of pensioners, especially those in their first retirement years, to labor activity and their influence in the labor market, especially in the segment of intellectual occupations.

Features of education for people of silver age

In this regard, silver universities will tend to strengthen professional training and retraining to the detriment of general education, enlightenment and mastering of userconsumer competencies (foreign languages, telephony, computer technology, etc.).

The most important problems of silver universities

In fact, the most important current problem of silver universities is their survival.

Project proposals and pre-project ideas

Crisis, stagnation, depression, recession are the best conditions for education, self-education, professional development, professional training and retraining, sharing experience, writing methods and textbooks - the whole long trail of retrospective reflection of accumulated experience. This should be done not because there are brighter times ahead (which is unlikely), but because it allows history to melt into culture. The longer the crisis lasts and the deeper it goes, the richer the cultural layer and educational potential will be.

This period should be the heyday of ageist pedagogy.

A foreseeable perspective

Ontological characterization of the period

Brazil will remain the only analog of Russia: vast unpopulated spaces, abundant natural resources, mostly poor and impoverished population concentrated in a few megacities, unflagging optimism and frenzied cheerfulness, flourishing of local initiatives, local self-government and self-employment with ineradicable corruption of official authorities at all levels.

Demographic trend

In the foreseeable future, there will be a marked rejuvenation of the population, both due to the high birth rate characteristic of the post-war baby boomers, as well as in the demographically similar situations of Brazil, Nigeria, Iran and China during the Cultural Revolution, accompanied by the intensive displacement of old people - due to lower living standards, deteriorating sanitary and hygienic conditions, changes in medical care and health care in general, such as a greater focus on the disabled than on the elderly.

Peculiarities of education for people of silver age

In the foreseeable future, the educational needs of people of silver age will be oriented toward:

- Seeking employment, including non-labor (volunteering, theater, music, Internet journalism, etc.)
- Seeking commercially viable self-employment, primarily in small business, but also handicrafts and cottage industries, IT and the Internet).

Critical issues for silver universities

The need for teaching and pedagogical staff will be sharply reduced. Silver universities will turn mainly into communication and socialization platforms with only educational elements or without them at all.

The educational function of silver universities will be largely unclaimed.

Project proposals and pre-project ideas

The most in demand in the foreseeable future will be:

- business incubators for pensioners and seniors
- medical, cognitive and ecological tourism
- alternative treatment and healthcare
- craft courses and workshops

Cite this article: Aleksandr Levintov. (2024) Problems and prospects of silver universities. *Advanced Educational Research & Reviews* 1 (1): 07-08

- Courses and programs for mutual education and self-education
- Political discussion and debate clubs

A distant perspective

Ontological characteristic of the period

The "golden billion" model is being realized: 1 billion people will live "as under communism", in very comfortable conditions and well-being, and the remaining billions will live in deep poverty. At the same time, every second inhabitant of Arabia, every tenth European, Japanese, American, Canadian, Australian, South Korean, Israeli, etc., every hundredth Chinese, every thousandth inhabitant of Russia, India, Bangladesh, Congo, Brazil, Zambia, etc. will be in the "golden billion".

Demographic trend

"Golden billion" will provide themselves longevity, approximately up to 1000 years, the remaining billions will gain immortality and in this regard, the actual people (age 30-50 years) and various kinds of cyborgs, robots, automatons will be little different from each other. Old age will be characteristic only for the "golden billion" and will have a duration of 200-300 years.

Features of education for people of silver age

Since in Russia, out of the estimated population of 50-100 million people, only 50-100 thousand people will belong to the "golden billion", of which people of silver age make up no more than a quarter (15-25 thousand people), the network of silver universities will be very sparse, especially if we take into account that it will be prestigious to receive silver education in the elite cultural centers of Europe, America and Asia.

The main content of silver education will be the aesthetic and artistic needs of people, above all art, namely mastering:

- mastery
- creativity
- combination of mastery and creativity

The most important problems of silver universities

Perhaps these will be the most difficult and unimaginable difficulties and complexities, especially for the modern level of performance - to satisfy the most whimsical and unexpected educational demands of a generation of people pampered and spoiled by wealth and comfort, who continuously seek not only novelty, but also the means of generating the new. To meet this crazy demand of these approximately 300 million people will consume half of all resources, forces and energies of mankind, including a huge plume of robots, cyborgs and other inanimate and quasi-animate intelligence.

Project proposals and pre-project ideas

The remoteness of this perspective is mainly ontological, not temporal, so it is important to search, collect, store and develop the most fantastic projects and ideas already now - they will be in demand. Thus, the Silver Universities should already be engaged in super-venture topics that have no practical significance and applicability at present.

Copyright: ©2024 Aleksandr Levintov. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.